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Crowd Chasing: A Critical Study of the Tension Between Quantitative Growth and Qualitative Spiritual Development in Christian Ministry

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Abstract

The term “crowd chasing” refers to the empirical study of the Christian ministry in the context of attracting a large group of people to a specific location for religious purposes or events, typically through various growth drives or evangelical outreaches. The research aims to arouse the inherent danger involved in the crave for a quantitative growth culture. As such, the paper traces the historical context in order to address the contemporary trends thereby exposing the significant ways crowd chasing deceives. Further, this research aims to exfoliate the intricate way crowd chasing has affected, influenced, and fueled the crave and craze for numbers and membership size, instead of qualitative spiritual development. The study utilized only primary sources, the local churches of the researcher, as a methodology to describe quantitative growth and qualitative spiritual development. Analysis explored correlates between qualitative spiritual development and quantitative growth dimensions. Also, relevant literature, provided the data required for the present research. The findings are substantiated by the significant results in the tension between quantitative growth culture and qualitative spiritual development. These findings are critical as well as necessary because they allow better understanding of the reasons for qualitative spiritual development and allow conclusions to be drawn for future spiritual development strategies. The research proposes and offers possible recommendations tailored to the unique context of the present-day church. Through this analysis, the paper concludes by advocating that the church must resist the temptation to equate success in ministry with the crowd.

Key words: local church, quantitative growth, qualitative development, crowd chasing, christian ministry.

1.0 Introduction

In present-day church contexts, the pressure to chase the crowd in order to grow in attendance figures often overshadows the more difficult work of qualitative spiritual development. Although crowd chasing is not essentially harmful, when metrics - a means of deriving a quantitative measurement or approximation for otherwise qualitative phenomena - become the exclusive measure of success, the church risk becoming institution of religious consumerism rather than a community of transformation.

The present-day church is doing everything possible to generate growth. The focus on quantity growth and more seemed right. But the cumulative negative consequences are now becoming apparent. The veneration of crowd is crushing the spirits of small churches, inflating the egos of the mega church, and creating a frenzied pursuit of numbers and the obsession of getting the crowd into the building. When numbers or crowd chasing take priority over qualitative spiritual development, there is a problem - an obsession. This obsession is causing the church to behave in ways that are not only unhelpful, but also inappropriate in magnitude. When crowd chasing is more important than integrity that is inappropriate and unreasonable.

1.1. Research Problem Statement

Today there is an unrelenting demand on churches to get the crowd faster. It is burning out ministers of the gospel, tempting them to compromise their values, and diverting attention from what matters most. In the present-day church, crowd define the faith community. That should not, but they do. The minister of the gospel leading a congregation of three thousand, for example, receives more credibility than a minister of the gospel of three hundred small congregational church.. Crowd is a craving that always demands more. An obsession with crowd chasing may be the least-acknowledged major contributor to pastors leaving ministry; pastors dealing with stress and burn out at record levels; moral compromise; and a long list of other church dysfunctions. Yet a church can witness exponential growth in attendance figures without compromising integrity. There are still a lot of deeply principled mega-church pastors. This paper explores the effects of prioritizing crowd chasing over qualitative spiritual development in Christian ministry.

1.2. Significance of the Study

At the heart of small congregational faith communities lies an unresolved tension, a dilemma that continues to disturb the members across the pew and the pulpit, the laity and the clergy. Despite the unique, divine call of these churches or faith communities, the members wrestle with a lingering crisis of attendance figures and membership sizes. This dilemma is not rooted in quantitative growth, but in the erosion of deep, qualitative spiritual development born from the culture of crowd chasing. This paper will contribute to theological and pastoral discourse by offering insights into the dangers of crowd chasing and advocating for a return to deep, qualitative

spiritual development. It will benefit pastors, church leaders, theological educators, and congregational communities.

2.0. Defining the Concepts

2.1. Crowd Chasing

Crowd Chasing means to draw or attract a large group of people to a specific location for religious purposes or events, typically through various evangelism drive or evangelical outreaches. A church can achieve this by offering members of the public something spectacular or desirable, whether it is an exciting church activity, a religious programme, or an engaging worship experience. The goal is to create a sense of pull, causing the local population to gather in the church and participate in their worship services or activities. Also, crowd chasing involves organizing religious activities with the intention to capture the attention of the local population and make them (want) to attend, experience, or be a part of the local church. The appeal can stem from various gospel programmes, such as praise concerts, medical outreaches, food welfare, or indoor and outdoor crusades. Crowd Chasing relies on generating enough interest or desire to overcome people's natural inclination to stay put.

2.2. Quantitative Growth

In Christianity, quantitative growth signifies an increase in the number of membership within the congregation or local assembly. It reflects a numerical expansion and or increase of the church, focusing on the measurable growth of its membership. This expansion can be tracked through metrics like baptism rates, church attendance figures, and overall membership counts, providing a quantifiable assessment of the development of the church. In Quantitative Growth, numbers are referenced because they provide physical evidence. Numbers are tangible verification to a church that something is happening. Numbers are evidence of process and progress, or lack of it.

2.3. Qualitative Spiritual Development

Qualitative Spiritual Development in Christian ministry refers to the deepening and transformation of an individual's faith and relationship with God, as experienced and understood through personal reflection, interaction with others, and engagement with spiritual practices.

This involves individuals exploring their own faith journey, examining their beliefs and values, and reflecting on their relationship with God. Qualitative spiritual development is not solely an individual pursuit, participation in activities like prayer, worship, Bible study, and acts of service are crucial for nurturing spiritual growth. Qualitative spiritual development aims for a deeper understanding of God, a more mature faith, and a life that reflects Christian values.

Church growth remains a central theme in Pentecostal missiology. Understanding the dynamics that foster qualitative spiritual development is critical, particularly within Pentecostal and Charismatic contexts.

2.4. Local Church

The English word "church" comes from the Greek word "kuriakon, originally meaning the "Lord's house" or the "Lord's place." But in time, it came to mean the people "who come to worship in the Lord's house." The English version translators used the English word "church " to translate the Greek word "ekkleesia," meaning an assembly or congregation of called out ones. In the Authorized Version of the Bible, also referred to as the King James Version, the word "church" is a reference to an assembly of called out ones, except for Acts 7: 38.

There are two usages of the Greek noun "ekkleesia" or church in the New Testament:

- i. The Universal Church - a spiritual body composed of believers of all ages and times who are united to God by faith in Jesus Christ (Eph. 1:2; 3:2; Heb. 12:23).
- ii. The Local Church - a visible body of believers united to God by faith in Jesus Christ.

A local church, therefore, is a company of professed Christians of a given community who voluntarily associate themselves and meet at regular times at a stated place for the purpose of helping to carry out the commission called, "The Great Commission," given to the universal church (Matthew 28: 19, 20). From this point onward, this paper shall continue its attention to this local or visible Church.

3.0. The Rise of Quantitative Growth Culture

3.1. Historical Context

The Great Commission mandate is to make disciples, not crowd chasing (Matthew 28:19–20). In fact, even as Jesus drew followers, He preached difficult truths that reduced their ranks (John 6:60–66).

According to the Book of Acts, “large numbers” converted to Christianity in Ephesus (19:26). The church in that city grew so rapidly pagan shrine makers felt threatened and started a riot (verses 23–41). Nevertheless, an assessment of the Ephesian church in Revelation offered no comment on the congregation’s size. Instead, the resurrected Jesus called on members to repent over forsaking their first love (2:1–7).

No honest reading of such passages can lead us to think the church is all about quantitative growth - crowd chasing or membership size - and amassing resources. Yet wealth and attendance figures have somehow become the measures of success among Pentecostal Churches, particularly in Nigeria and Africa in general. By this metric, growth and strength are synonymous with quantitative growth or numerical increase. If a congregation is not seeing an annual uptick in attendance, it is assumed that the church is stuck, broken, or dying — regardless of its health.

When quantitative growth take priority over qualitative spiritual development, there is a problem - an obsession. And this obsession for crowd chasing is causing the church leaders to behave in ways that are not only unhelpful, but also inappropriate.

3.2 Contemporary Trends

Of course, there is nothing inherently wrong with large congregations. Reaching more people with the gospel is a good thing. Yet today there is an unrelenting demand on churches to get the crowd and have the figures grow, faster. It is burning out pastors, tempting leaders to compromise their values. Growth is not the problem; quantity is. Quantity is an attitude, not a number. It is a mindset that prioritizes becoming bigger over being biblical. Pastors who are crowd chasers frequently get a pass on problematic behaviour. Believers shrug and say, like the researcher have heard several times from some ministers within and outside his local assembly that, “The church is growing, so they must be doing something right.”

One time while discussing the state of the local church with a couple of ministers and pastors in his congregation, the researcher recalls the following exchange when they mentioned a particular church in his district and another one outside his jurisdiction and said, “Those churches are successful. They are growing like crazy, doing some of the things that we are doing.” But their preaching is terrible — not at all what we teach. When quantitative growth is more important than qualitative spiritual development, it is not suitable for the situation. In recent years, Christians have become almost immune to the shock of pastors failing morally. On numerous occasions, the researcher have heard key members and ministers of such local assembly say, aftermath of such situations, “That is just how our pastor was. He was known to be a little crude, but no one challenged him on it because the church was growing.”

4.0. A Critical Study of the Tension

In the present-day church, numbers define the congregation; it defines a local assembly. They should not, but they do. The pastor leading a congregation of three thousand receives more credibility than a pastor of three hundred — and considerably more than a pastor of thirty. The Church has an unhealthy relationship with quantitative growth. And it’s destroying the church. Pastors are leaving ministry over their inability to get the attendance figures up. Those who remain are dealing with stress and burnout at record levels.

Quantitative growth is a craving that always demands more. An obsession with membership size may be the least-acknowledged major contributor to pastoral departures, ministerial burnout, congregational division, moral compromise, and a long list of other church dysfunctions. How did we get here? Donald McGavran was an American missionary to India from 1923–54. McGavran introduced a number of terms and ideas that are part of Pentecostal language today, including the phrase “church growth.” In fact, this book has been called the Magna Carta - a landmark document that sets out rights or important principles - of the church growth movement. This is universally considered the spark that started the church growth movement.

What did pastors do with the lessons from church growth movement? They turned it into a race to outgrow the church next door. Preachers who could draw the biggest crowds and raise the most money, built the biggest churches. Thus, the model of the entrepreneurial pastors was born. These entrepreneurial pastors applied McGavran's missional ideas and terminology to their theological context. This explains why most church growth conferences over the past 20 years have featured leaders of the biggest congregations. Pastors from smaller settings gather to learn the secrets of increasing attendance. There is little interest in gleaning wisdom from faithful, small-church leaders. Pastors want to hear from those who have seemingly arrived — so they, too, can grow their churches bigger, faster.

4.1. The Significant Ways Crowd Chasing Deceives

Crowd Chasing is deceptive. It's easy to feel justified in everything you have done when the numbers are up. Crowd Chasing acts as its own merit system. There are, at least, four significant ways crowd chasing deceives.

4.1.1. Crowd chasing contributes to overconfidence

There is an inverse relationship between confidence and actual knowledge. We start our ministry training with little knowledge and little confidence. As we learn, our confidence soars to the peak of overconfidence. Having gone through a couple of years of pastoring, after we have had some hard-earned experience, the reality of ministry complexity kicks in and our confidence plummets to the valley of underconfidence. This is where many ministers and ministries quit. But those who persist, persevere, and keep going have the chance to enter the slope of experience, in which their experience and confidence rise at the same rate. Persistence and perseverance are the keys to long-term ministry. Eventually, those who stick with it arrive at the plateau of sustainability. At that point, confidence is high again, and they become overconfident in their own abilities.

4.1.2. Crowd chasing leads to a shallow view of what makes a church healthy

Many ministers have a shallow, one-dimensional view of what makes a church healthy. They perceive congregational size and health as a continuum, with smaller churches on the unhealthy end and bigger ones on the healthy side. The assumption is that church health increases or decreases in proportion to attendance figure. No wonder we think of big churches as healthy and assume their leaders are always worth following. And conclude that the churches that have not grown numerically in a while must be stuck, broken and unhealthy. We figure someone needs to fix or close these congregations. Certainly, we do not expect to learn anything from their leaders — except perhaps what not to do.

4.1.3. Crowd chasing leads to loss of interest in divine direction in critical moments

During the wake of the pandemic, it was noticed and witnessed how some leaders of the churches with crowd and mega membership sizes told their congregation not to leave their homes for church

services so as not to be infected by the spread of the virus. They lost interest in divine direction and what God feels about their lives and became conscious of the reports of medical scientists. They had no interest in the report of the Lord. Instead of seeking the mind of God, everyone was conscious of what medical scientists had to say at that given period. The church fell short of the glory of God. His power left the altar and everyone lost His direction.

4.1.4. Crowd chasing leads to modernization of the life of Christ

There are obvious deviations in crowd chasing. This accounts for the decadence predominant in such Christian faith community. They have become so philosophical to the extent that their attention and objectivity have been so overwhelmed by the world around them. It is an errant fallacy to talk about modernization of the life of Christ in order to promote the activities of the church. By this the Christian ministry play into the intrigues of the enemy.

5.0. Enhancing Qualitative Spiritual Development in Christian Ministry

We can enhance qualitative spiritual development in Christian ministry through the following approaches:

5.1. Prioritizing Purpose Over Crowd Chasing

Beneath the rave and crave for mega membership size lies a critical question: are we still aligned with the purpose of Christ? Or have we become performers on a stage of misplaced priorities? This question calls for a spiritual re-calibration, one that reclaims the redemptive voice and mission of the church.

5.1.1. Challenging Misplaced Values and a Misaligned Church

The present-day church is increasingly marked by affluence, celebrity culture, and a theology of materialism, not biblical prosperity.

5.1.2. Symptoms of a Misaligned Church

i. Lavish Displays: It is becoming fashionable that mega church pastors must be carried in private jets when they are invited to a speaking engagement; received by a motorcade of assorted limousines or SUV; publicized on giant and electronic bill boards on strategic locations in the city and many more; while communities hosting some of this mega churches languish in poverty.

ii. Materialism Gospel (Mistaken for Prosperity Gospel): A distorted message that equates faith with financial gain, reducing God to a vending machine of blessings. Every seed must be sowed only in the life of the pastor before the Lord will prosper the giver.

iii. Status-Driven Leadership: Ordination and Ecclesiastical titles are now often based on affluence and influence, not spiritual maturity, calling or service.

5.2. Discarding The Culture of Crowd Chasing

Church leaders must put more effort of their time and energy into discipleship than crowd chasing. For decades, church leaders have taught pastoral competence. Conference after conference has promoted methods, ideas, innovations and technologies. Unfortunately, while emphasizing technical competence, integrity has often been taken for granted. The church can no longer ignore this issue. The lure of quantitative growth brings temptation to compromise discipleship and integrity.

5.3. Returning to the Destiny of The Church

The destiny of the church is three fold:

- a. To be married as a chaste virgin to Christ (Rev. 21:9; 2 Cor. 11:2; Eph. 5:27).
- b. To reign with Christ as a Royal Consort (Rev. 1:6; 3:21; 1 Pet. 2:9; Rev. 20:6).
- c. To show forth the praise, the grace, and the glory of God (Eph. 1:6-12; 3:10).

6.0. Recommendations

Based on the findings of this paper, the researcher proposes improvements, and offers recommendations tailored to the unique context of the ongoing discourse, viz:

6.1. The Need to Set God-Sized Vision, Not Crowd-Sized Vision

We keep hearing that churches become great by writing strong mission statements and setting huge goals, and then pursuing them. As the theory goes, an objective that does not scare you is too small, and a plan without a huge numerical component is doomed to failure. There is a place to make plans and set goals, but we don't need to cast a crowd-sized vision. Jesus gave us the biggest vision of all - to live and share the gospel, which is, redeeming creation back to the Creator (Rom. 8:19 - 23). The problem with crowd chasing is not that it is too big and huge. Rather, it is too small. This vision may be crowd-sized, but it is not God-sized.

6.2. The Need to Act with Integrity

When crowd chasing is the goal, acting with integrity sometimes feels like a roadblock. Crowd chasing has a pull. It exerts a force that threatens to consume and control everyone and everything. The obsession for numbers lead to breach of integrity. It may help gain crowd, but it is causing a lot more to leave church. They are walking away because they see too much distance between what pastors say and do.

6.3. The Need to Embody the Quiet Power of Purpose

The Church must resist the temptation to mirror the world's obsession with spectacle and instead embody the quiet power of purpose. Three simple actions stand out.

- i. **Simplicity in Worship:** Let our gatherings reflect humility and reverence towards God, not human worship and too much technicality.
- ii. **Stewardship Over Showmanship:** Redirect resources toward missions, education, and community development.
- iii. **Servant Leadership:** Reclaim the model of Christ, who washed feet rather than demanded thrones.

6.4. The Need for Spiritual Formation and Character Development

The Christian ministry should place a strong emphasis on the personal spiritual growth and character development of the members. This goes beyond charisma to ensure that members develop strong ethical, spiritual, and leadership qualities. Mentorship programmes, spiritual retreats, and ministry training are incorporated into the ministry activity to cultivate the spiritual maturity needed for effective ministry.

6.5. The Need to Rearrange Requirements for Church Leaders

As pastors called to tend God's flock, we must stop overlooking flaws in favour of numerical increase. The biblical requirements for church leaders have nothing to do with quantitative growth, but everything to do with character (1 Tim. 3:1-7; Tit. 1:6-9). Jesus cautioned His disciples to focus on the condition of the soul rather than the size of their barns (Lk. 12:16-21).

7.0. Conclusion

The author has been able to distinguish between quantitative Growth and Qualitative Spiritual development in Christian ministry. The researcher asserts that the church must resist the temptation to equate success in ministry with crowd. While quantitative growth can be a sign of life, it is not the definitive measure of health. Qualitative spiritual development is central to the mission of the church. Only by prioritizing qualitative spiritual development can the church truly fulfill its calling.

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